

Diversity Equity Inclusion

Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) Management Framework for Smaller Firms (SME) in Europe: A Practical Guide

Status & Suggested Actions | 2026

Prepared by Aušrinė Šilenskytė and Aaron Kiverä (University of Vaasa, Finland).

Status was defined by utilizing insights from a larger study conducted by DEI4SME project team. Please access the complete report <https://dei4sme.eu/dei4sme-report/>. Actions were suggested drawing on research conducted at the University of Vaasa and by analysing insights obtained through focus group discussions conducted by DEI4SME project partners. Read more about focus group discussions: <https://dei4sme.eu/dei4sme-newsletter-3-has-been-published/>

1. What is the status of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) in Smaller Firms in Europe?

Two complementary surveys one focused on SME decision-makers and the other on employees with data collected in Austria, Finland, Germany, and Lithuania, offer a nuanced view into the current state of DEI in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) across Europe.

The **SME survey** reveals a general awareness of DEI, with 59.8% expressing a desire to learn how it supports business outcomes. However, implementation lags: 74.4% report lacking the resources to meaningfully engage in DEI, only 12% have a designated DEI officer, and just 5.8% consider themselves DEI experts. Notably, when asked about the presence of marginalized groups in their workforce, many SMEs responded with “I don’t know,” highlighting a widespread absence of data or monitoring.

The **individual survey** provides a contrasting but equally revealing perspective. Employees across identity groups expressed moderate-to-high satisfaction with workplace fairness in areas like performance evaluation and training. Yet responses also show persistent gaps in inclusion and structural support. For instance, 62% of individuals said they experienced no gender identity bias during recruitment, and 66% felt fully included at work positive signals. However, inclusion dropped sharply for LGBTQIA+ employees, with only 41% feeling recruitment was bias-free and 34% satisfied with workplace accommodations. Similar disparities were seen for employees with disabilities (37% felt fully included), and religious and ethnic minorities, especially in Austria. Across nearly all identity groups, one common issue emerges: 30–45% of respondents reported not knowing whether their company monitors or measures DEI, revealing a gap.

The two surveys illustrate a shared but uneven DEI landscape. SMEs generally signal interest but lack strategy, while employees frequently encounter underdeveloped or invisible initiatives. Notably, the biggest differences and challenges were observed in Austria, but other researched countries Finland, Germany, and Lithuania were showing similar trends, but not in all dimensions.

2. What can be done to address current challenges in SMEs who often lack resources and capabilities to address DEI issues?

There is the disconnect between the political framing of DEI and its practical relevance for businesses—especially SMEs. DEI is often poorly defined and shaped more by personal attitudes than by strategic intent. Although the EU promotes DEI through regulation, a clear gap remains between policy and business practice. Bridging this divide requires not only cultural change but also concrete, accessible approaches that demonstrate the value of DEI in everyday operations. Below we reflect on some specific issues and ways to address them in the SME context.

2.1. DEI IN THE MANAGEMENT OF THE FIRM

Only 5.8% of SMEs identify as DEI experts, and 39.4% see no observable benefit. On the other hand, only 33.4% believe DEI is genuinely embedded in their company’s mission, vision, or values. By contrast, 34.5% explicitly disagreed with that statement, and another 25.3% were

neutral, suggesting that DEI may exist as rhetoric rather than reality. These doubts extend to practical experience: while many SMEs (66.6%) claim to value diverse perspectives in daily operations, the employee survey shows that less than 60% of employees feel that diverse perspectives are encouraged and valued in daily- and strategic-decision making; only 65% said management provides a safe space for expressing differing views, and just 63% felt able to openly express personal or cultural differences without fear of judgment. Meanwhile, only 64% felt comfortable reporting inclusion-related concerns, and 73% said they knew where to report such issues. This gap between perceived inclusion and structural reinforcement is strengthened as only a third of all respondents report DEI as part of their company’s identity, and even less report having benefitted from practises related to DEI management. When employees are unsure whether DEI is backed by values, process, and leadership, engagement weakens and the risk of turnover increases.

The SMEs could fix this situation with only minor effort: by conducting business meetings in an inclusive manner, inviting different, including conflicting opinions to be shared openly; by creating spaces for employees suggest different ways of doing things in the company or offering a space to leave a note on suggested improvements in all spheres of business operations and management and discussing how these suggestions have been considered.

2.2. COMPLIANCE, SYMBOLIC CHECKLIST OR SOMETHING MORE?

While many SMEs consider themselves compliant, employee perspectives suggest that DEI ownership is often inadequate or even absent. Across the surveyed countries, nearly 38% of employees said no one in their company is formally responsible for DEI, and only about 12% reported dedicated DEI roles outside of HR. Most often, responsibility falls to HR departments, which may lack the authority or resources to drive systemic change. Very few organizations use external support (2%) or technological tools (2%) to manage issues related to DEI. In line with this, less than 10% view their company as a DEI expert, and the majority identify their workplace are just DEI compliant or developing. Strikingly, 12% described their employer as lacking DEI awareness completely.

These results suggest that **SMEs need** effective, easy to use tools to address diversity management and educational materials how this relates to the local and the EU regulatory framework.

2.3. CHOOSING LOCAL APPROACH TO DEI IN SMEs

The differences between studied countries underscore the need for localized DEI strategies. In Austria, 58.8% of employees said they had not benefitted from DEI at work. In Germany, the inverse was true: 53% reported clear benefits. Finland and Lithuania reported stronger results across multiple dimensions, from training access to career development¹.

This means that **SMEs should preferably choose to manage DEI by considering their local context** and local social and business needs – differences even in the same region – the EU – may still be large. Where values-based framing is met with resistance, SMEs could emphasize compliance to local and international DEI and related regulations, retention, or operational

¹ These variations can be interpreted through Institutional Theory, which suggests organizations reflect the pressures and norms of their external environment.

resilience. Where openness exists, DEI can be linked to psychological safety and employee engagement. A one-size-fits-all model is not only ineffective but also counterproductive.

2.4. TACKLING AWARENESS GAPS AND STEREOTYPES

The frequent “I don’t know” responses from SMEs about the presence of marginalized employees parallel employees’ own uncertainty about DEI policy and invites for action. This mutual opacity suggests that individuals recognize and affirm their in-group more readily than those who differ². The result is a workplace where difference is technically present but organizationally invisible. Introducing anonymous perception-based inclusion surveys can surface early signs of exclusion without requiring demographic disclosure but are likely to be challenging in an SME context. Stereotype threat supports the idea that individuals who feel their identities are undervalued may underperform or disengage. Without cues that affirm identity safety, expression may feel performative or forced.

SMEs could consider practices such as: openly welcoming the employees to express their identity with preferred apparel attributes (e.g., symbols, signs, and national clothing elements); personalizing their working space with things that matter to them; creating small occasions to celebrate other than traditional festivals; having a post-it wall with anonymous suggestions for joint activities and feedback on inclusion, among others. Also, embedding small, visible cues (such as affirming language during onboarding, inclusive signage, public diversity statements, representation of diverse individuals in internal materials, and accessible codes of conduct) send powerful signals that indicate that inclusion is not just a policy but a culture. These interventions may address the recognition deficit that undermines engagement and retention and create the trust required to begin building them. Bias interrupters, such as ensuring balanced speaking time or reviewing performance metrics for bias patterns, provide a corrective lens. SMEs that adopt such tools see fewer blind spots in decision-making and stronger adaptive capacity in complex environments.

2.5. INCLUSIVE HIRING AND PROMOTION

The SME data show a preference for informal recruitment practices, while employees, especially caregivers, students, and those with disabilities, report gaps in fair access. Overall, only 49% of ethnic minority respondents reported unbiased recruitment experiences; similarly, of those providing care, only half report unbiased and fair recruitment processes. For individuals with disabilities, the situation is even more dire, as only 37% report fair and unbiased hiring and promotion practices. Hiring for “fit” often translates into reproducing sameness and therefore fewer opportunities to be hired and promoted for employees with more complex identities³. Behavioural design strategies like anonymized CV screening or team interviews interrupt these cognitive defaults but are hard to implement in an SME context because these tools may be costly, or there might be only one manager who takes hiring decisions.

SMEs could consider practices, such as: structured interview and [performance evaluation](#) rubrics that define competencies needed for the position; task-based hiring when applicants should show their ability to perform a certain task; and using signalling words in job advertisements that indicate firms’ flexibility to consider diverse applicants. These and other

² In alignment with Social Identity Theory (Tajfel & Turner)

³ The Similarity-Attraction Paradigm

small, but effective actions enhance fairness by design and demonstrate the organization's commitment to inclusion in action, not just intention.

2.6. EQUALITY OR EQUITY OR INCLUSION?

Indicating that broad intentions are not translating into targeted impact, especially when minor accommodations are needed to focus on work matters rather than personal discomfort. For example, only 53% of respondents felt their religious accommodation needs were met, for the Age subgroup 62% report accommodations, and 25% of respondents with disability felt supported in development. Similarly, only 59% of those providing care claim to have required accommodations provided. Therefore, sometimes to achieve best performance, minor accommodations may need to be considered.

The gap between intention and reception **underscores the need to move from equal treatment to equitable interventions**. Adapting policy flexibility, allowing culturally responsive accommodations, and acknowledging different workplace experiences can shift the dynamic from performative inclusion to actual belonging. While many accommodations may be costly, others are more a cognitive barrier.

When it comes to **inclusion**, 77% of employees say they feel generally valued and included at work, but with only 37% of employees with disabilities and 34% of LGBTQIA+ respondents report feeling fully included, the need for visibility tools is clear. The gap between being seen and being supported is especially stark for employees with visible minority identities. While 66% of employees felt generally included by gender identity, only a bit more than a third of employees with more marginalized identities report the same.

For SME managers, the implications are clear: inclusion reduces biases within groups, stabilizes teams, improves recruitment quality & reduces costs, it also aligns the organization with emerging social and institutional expectations, which can be revenue boosting via engagement with minorities. In short, DEI does not have to be a cost, it can be a safeguard and potentially even generate income through small practices, such as creating psychological safety at work to avoid retentions, creating equal opportunities to receive training at work, or appreciating diverse ways of achieving goals.

3. Framework for managing DEI in SMEs in Europe

It is evident that SMEs around Europe have different skills, motivations, and external environments to engage with DEI. DEI is also a social concept, which means that discovering its meaning, benefits, and ways to manage it may take time and reflection. Thus, to group the above-mentioned actions in a meaningful way, we developed a **practical framework comprising four areas of engagement with diversity management in SMEs** (Figure 1).

The key aspect of the suggested framework concerns moving towards the integration of DEI matters to the core business rather than addressing them as a part of the separate, supporting, voluntary actions. SMEs can improve their engagement in any or all of these areas.

For SMEs who wish to implement this framework in practice, we recommend using an **open access digital tool for social sustainability**: <https://tool.dei4sme.eu>. This tool has been designed to help firms engage in all four areas identified in this framework and report on their actions.

Figure 1. Framework for diversity management in SMEs in Europe: A Practical Guide